

Simple Titrimetric Method for the Determination of Oxydemton-Methyl, Formothion and Dimethoate in Insecticide Formulations and in Admixtures

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Oxydemtonmethyl (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S*-[2-ethylsulphinyl]-ethylthiophosphate) (1), formothion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S*-[*N*-methyl-*N*-formylcarbonylmethyl]dithiophosphate) (2) and dimethoate (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S*-[*N*-methylcarbonylmethyl]dithiophosphate) (3) are commercially important

1

2; R = CHO
3; R = H

insecticides. The methods¹ commonly used for the analysis of these insecticides are time-consuming and require strict control of experimental conditions. This creates a need for a convenient and rapid method for their analysis. That these insecticides on alkaline hydrolysis yield alkali mono/dithiophosphates² which can be determined through oxidimetric titrations with potassium iodate in acidic medium, has been made the basis of a titrimetric method for their determination. The method has been successfully applied to the analysis of these insecticides in commercial formulations.

Whereas potassium iodate oxidises alkali monothio-phosphate (4) (hydrolytic product of oxydemtonmethyl, 1) with a single-electron change, the oxidation of alkali dithiophosphate (6) (hydrolytic product of formothion and dimethoate 2 and 3) involves three-electron change :

4

5

6

5

It is worthwhile to mention here that the disulphides (5) are also important insecticides and are in fact synthesised by the oxidation of the corresponding thiophosphates³. Based on their different oxidation behaviour with the same

agent, it is not only possible to distinguish oxydemton-methyl from formothion or dimethoate but also to analyse mixture containing oxydemtonmethyl and formothion (or dimethoate) using the relationships,

$$\text{Weight of oxydemtonmethyl (mg)} = \frac{M_1 M_2}{3M_1 - M_2} \left(\frac{3W}{M_2} - VN \right)$$

Weight of formothion or dimethoate (mg) =

$$W - \frac{M_1 M_2}{3M_1 - M_2} \left(\frac{3W}{M_2} - VN \right)$$

where *V* denotes the volume (ml) of *N* oxidant solution consumed by *W* weight (mg) of the mixture of oxydemton-methyl and formothion or dimethoate and *M*₁ and *M*₂ stand for molecular weights of oxydemtonmethyl and formothion or dimethoate respectively.

The noticeable feature of this mixture analysis is that a single titration with the reagent performed on a single aliquot can analyse the mixture for both the components.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) show that overall maximum relative standard deviation (RSD) calculated with 6 and 18 mg of each insecticide is 0.70%. The commercial formulations based on these insecticides when analysed by the proposed method gave recoveries in the range 98.3–99.6% with RSD's in the range 0.2–0.4% (Table 2). Synthetic mixtures of oxydemton-methyl and formothion and oxydemtonmethyl and dimethoate with proportions of the components ranging from 1 : 4 to 4 : 1 could be analysed with maximum RSD of 0.85% for oxydemton-methyl, for both mixtures, 0.75% for formothion, and 0.70% for dimethoate.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF OXYDEMTONMETHYL, FORMOTHION AND DIMETHOATE*

Insecticide	Amount found (mg) ^a		Amount found (mg) ^b	
	Visual method	Poten. method	Visual method	Poten. method
Oxydemton-methyl	5.97 (0.042)	6.05 (0.042)	17.92 (0.064)	18.05 (0.063)
Formothion	6.04 (0.038)	6.01 (0.034)	17.94 (0.062)	17.97 (0.068)
Dimethoate	5.95 (0.040)	5.97 (0.036)	18.07 (0.066)	19.96 (0.058)

*Values are mean of ten determinations with standard deviation (±) in parenthesis.

^aAmount taken = 6.0 mg. ^bAmount taken = 18.0 mg.

TABLE 2—ASSAY RESULTS OF COMMERCIAL FORMULATIONS OF OXYDEMTON-METHYL, FORMOTHION AND DIMETHOATE

Formulation	Based on active ingredient (%)	Active ingredient found (%) [*]			
		Visual method	Poten. method	Comparison method ^a	
Oxydemtonmethyl	II	25	24.7 (0.3)	24.8 (0.2)	24.5 (0.4)
	II	25	24.6 (0.4)	24.7 (0.3)	24.4 (0.5)
Formothion	I	25	24.6 (0.2)	24.9 (0.4)	24.6 (0.3)
Dimethoate	I	30	29.5 (0.3)	29.7 (0.2)	29.2 (0.6)
	II	30	29.6 (0.4)	29.6 (0.3)	29.3 (0.4)

^{*}Values are mean of five determination with standard deviation ($\pm$) in parenthesis. ^aRef. 1.

Experimental

Potentiometric titrations were performed on a Toshniwal CLO6A potentiometer equipped with a Pt-SCE assembly. Dimethylformamide (B.D.H.) was purified by keeping it over anhydrous sodium carbonate (A.R.) for 2 days and collecting the fraction distilled at 148.5–149.5°. KIO_3 (0.02 *N*) and KOH (0.1 *N*) solutions were prepared in water. The insecticides were procured from the manufacturer and their purity was checked¹.

Determination of oxydemtonmethyl, formothion and dimethoate : An aliquot (in dimethylformamide) of each

insecticide was mixed with KOH solution (2 ml) and kept for 5 min, then mixed with 3 *N* H_2SO_4 and the volume made to 20 ml with the acid. Dimethylformamide was then added dropwise till the turbid solution became clear. The solution was titrated visually and potentiometrically against standard (0.02 *N*) KIO_3 solution. In visual titrations, the end-point was marked the appearance of yellow colour. In potentiometric titrations, sharp jump in potential was observed at the equivalence point. Samples of insecticide formulations and mixtures were analysed by the proposed method as above.

References

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